

Social And Security Impacts Of ‘War on Terror’ On Pakistan

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 29, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: July 30, 2021</p> <p>Keywords : Militancy, Pakistani Taliban, Sectarian Violence, Terrorism, Tribal Areas</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7199716</p>	<p><i>Pakistan’s engagement in the US led ‘War on Terror’ adversely impacted its internal security landscape. In June 2014, Pakistan army launched operation Zarb-e-Azb in North Waziristan along Pak-Afghan border to improve internal security situation. This study assesses the social and security impacts of militancy and terrorism on Pakistan between 2001 and June 2014. The study argues that Pakistan’s internal security landscape was complicated by four trends: (i) birth of new militant organizations and splinter groups in post 9/11 era, (ii) the rise of Pakistani Taliban in the tribal areas, (iii) the increased linkages between terrorism, illicit drug trade and organized crime and (iv) the emergence of Al-Qaeda-Punjabi Taliban-Tehreek-e-Taliban Pakistan (TTP) Nexus. The article examines the strategy of this Nexus and its implications for Pakistan. It argues that Al-Qaeda-Punjabi Taliban-TTP Nexus was involved in increasing incidents of terrorism, sectarian and sub-sectarian violence. It carried out attacks on Western interests in Pakistan and used Pakistani territory to plan terrorist plots against United States and the Western countries. The article finds that Pakistan’s campaign against terrorism resulted in deepening sectarianism and violent extremism, growing crime-terror nexus and radicalization of segments of Pakistani society.</i></p>

Introduction

Pakistan’s engagement in the US-led ‘War on Terror’ worsened Pakistan’s internal security milieu. Pakistan military and paramilitary forces remained constantly engaged in a fierce battle with Al-Qaeda and affiliates in erstwhile Federally Administered Tribal Areas (FATA—now part of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP) province) of the country, which cost Pakistan heavy human, material and financial losses. Nevertheless, since 2001, Pakistan witnessed birth of new militant organizations and splinter groups. In 2007, Tehreek-e-Taliban Pakistan (TTP) was established which became one of Pakistan’s lethal militant organizations and since then, a Nexus between Al-Qaeda, TTP and Punjab based militant emerged which intensified its attacks in tribal belt and later expanded activities across the country. Worst still, militants utilized illicit drug trade and criminal networks to finance their activities. As a result, Pakistan witnessed a rising wave of extremism, terrorism and sectarian violence. The suicide bombers spread across Pakistan and the key military and civilian installations became vulnerable targets. Al-Qaeda, TTP and Punjab based militants’ Nexus also targeted interests of United States and the Western countries using Pakistan’s territory hence, further complicating Pakistan’s security landscape and damaging its interests in the region and beyond. On June 15, 2014, Pakistan military launched Operation Zarb-e-Azb in North Waziristan which dismantled and disrupted TTP and its affiliates and consequently *the terrorist attacks have substantially reduced.*

This article assesses the threats of militancy and terrorism to Pakistan’s internal security between 2001 and June 2014. It first analyses emergence of new militant groups following Pakistan’s decision to join the US-led ‘War on Terror.’ It then examines the emergence of Pakistani Taliban, in particular the rise of TTP in tribal areas. The next part describes the emergence of Al-Qaeda-Punjabi Taliban-TTP Nexus’, its strategy and implications for Pakistan’s security. The fourth part details the activities of the nexus between militants, drug traffickers and criminals. The final section concludes the article.

DISCUSSION: PAKISTAN’S ENGAGEMENT IN THE US-LED ‘WAR ON TERROR’ AND ITS IMPLICATIONS FOR INTERNAL SECURITY ENVIRONMENT

Growing militancy, sectarianism and terrorism were the main security threats that Pakistan faced from the 9/11 developments.

1. Birth of New Militant Organizations and Splinter Groups

The US invasion of Afghanistan in October 2001 and the ouster of Afghan Taliban from power in December 2001 deeply infuriated Pakistani militant groups and some of the lower cadres of Pakistan’s military, specially,

its intelligence agencies given that Afghan Taliban had extensive links with Inter-Services Intelligence Directorate (ISID), madaris (Islamic religious schools), militant groups, political parties and business community in Pakistan (Rashid, 2002, p. 185). Scores of fighters of Pakistani militant groups were based in Afghanistan when the 'War on Terror' commenced. They were hard hit, losing important commanders and hundreds of warriors to US-led coalition carpet bombings. For instance, Harkat-ul-Jihad-e-Islami (HuJI) suffered huge human losses and as many as 340 fighters of HuJI were killed in Afghanistan (Rashid, 2009, p. 60).

In January 2002, General Musharraf yielded to American pressure and banned five prominent militant organizations. Following the capture of a large number of militants of these organizations; the middle and lower cadre militants of these groups lost contact with their leadership, attained complete freedom from 'official control' and were swayed by Al-Qaeda's "call to arms." It could be argued that Pakistan military had miscalculated that militants would recognize Pakistan's security compulsions whereby Al-Qaeda and sectarian groups were attacked while Afghan Taliban were assisted (Haque, 2011; Shahzad, 2010). However, extremist and militant groups turned against Musharraf government for throwing its support behind the US-led coalition. Rana (2010), a political and security analyst, notes that on January 30, 2002, several newspapers in Pakistan received a leaflet from a new militant group 'Al-Saiqa.' The leaflet depicted Pakistan "as Darul Harb (Abode of War) and Darul Kufr (Abode of the Infidels), asking the people to wage *Jihad* against the government and its security forces." The message from Al-Saiqa indicated that militant groups turned against the government and security forces. A few days after the release of this leaflet, a new group, Lashkar-e-Omer, claimed responsibility for attack on a church in Bahawalpur. Moreover, in 2004, when General Musharraf started a peace process with India, Kashmir focused militant groups like Lashkar-e-Tayyaba (LT) and Jaish-e-Mohammad (JM) were put in deep freeze due to immense US pressure. Pakistan's decision to 'demobilize' Kashmiri militants in 2003-2004 and closing of the ISI's 'Kashmir Cell' without "extensive de-weaponization or rehabilitation" compelled these groups to move to erstwhile FATA. In 2006, the then ISI Director General, General Ashfaq Parvez Kayani's decision to wind up Kashmiri militant camps which were located in various parts of Hazara in KP and Pakistan's administered Azad Jammu & Kashmir (AJK), strengthened the nexus between Kashmir focused militant groups and Taliban. Scores of these well-trained militants began to pop up throughout Swat and tribal areas, particularly, in tribal areas of Waziristan and Darra Adam Khel. Splinter groups of LT and JM joined hands with Maulvi Fazlullah in Swat for refuge and for training local militants (Haque, 2011). In 2009, it was reported that eight breakaway factions of JM were involved in fighting Pakistan military in tribal areas (Waraich, 2009). In fact, small, splinter militant groups emerged with new names since 2009, these groups included: Badar Mansoor, Al-Furqan, Al-Mukhtar, Al-Qittal, Al-Azam Brigade, Asian Tigers, Janood-ul-Hafsa, Lashkar-e-Baluchistan, Punjabi Mujahideen, Itihad-e-Mujahideen Khurasan (IMK) and Al-Qittal. Some of these groups focused on ever more specific kinds of attacks. For instance, Asian Tigers focused on kidnappings; IMK sought to kill spies and government agents who provided information that led US Central Intelligence Agency (CIA)-operated drones to their targets in tribal belt; and Al-Qittal (Fight against Infidels) specialized in target killings. Security analysts believed that these splinter groups helped solve the militants' safety and financial problems (Babar, 2011).

2. The Rise of 'Pakistani Taliban' in Tribal Areas

Pakistani Taliban phenomenon finds the primary reason of its existence in the Afghan resistance against the US-led coalition. A defensive *Jihad* against Pakistani security forces was considered essential in order to guarantee Taliban survival in Pakistan, following Islamabad's decision to join the US-led 'War on Terror' (Franco, 2009, p. 289). To compound the challenge in tribal areas, the October 2002 elections saw the Mutahida Majlis-e-Amal (MMA) came to power in Balochistan and Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province. Two important factions of MMA: Jamiat Ulema-e-Islam, Fazal-ur-Rehman faction (JUI-F) and Jamiat Ulema-e-Islam, Samiul Haq faction (JUI-S) were closely linked with Afghan Taliban and were "sympathetic to their cause." Not surprisingly, this development led to an increase in attacks on US and North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) forces in Afghanistan in the spring of 2003. As early as 2003, "a loose coalition of like-minded" and tribal affiliated militants had emerged under the Pakistani Taliban label. They resented the US-led Operation Enduring Freedom (OEF) in Afghanistan and were determined to implement 'Islamic Sharia' in the tribal areas. The insurgency in tribal areas gathered momentum in 2004 when, General Musharraf sent troops in North and South Waziristan to combat Al-Qaeda and affiliates. The military intervention and operations of Pakistan army "helped generate more recruits and support for Taliban" (Cassidy, 2012, pp. 70-71). In fact, since 2004, Baitullah Mehsud, who became the Chief of the Tehreek-e-Taliban Pakistan (TTP) in 2007 (the year TTP was established officially), began enforcing Taliban-interpretation of Sharia in South Waziristan (Rana, 2008). Against this backdrop, the MMA demonstrated its support for Afghan Taliban and other militant groups by opposing military action against them and instead, favouring negotiating peace settlement with the militants in North and South

Waziristan. The actual effect of the accords was more protection and room for maneuver for the Taliban in Pak-Afghan border areas (Kjaernet & Torjesen, 2008, p. 8).

To gain control over an area, Pakistani Taliban formulated a four-point strategy. This strategy encompassed political, administrative, economic and social aspects. As a first step, they cracked down on criminals and taxed people to collect money for their activities. Second, they executed or expelled powerful tribal chieftains, who could challenge the authority of Taliban. Seeking to exercise their control, Taliban influenced by the ideology of Al-Qaeda had killed influential Maliks (tribal elders). Third, they established a parallel justice system for corruption free, simple and quick dispensation of justice. Fourth, they selected their trusted men as administrators in tribal areas. Rana (2008) noted that “their strategy eroded the traditional concept of collective responsibility, which adversely affected the political administration” in tribal areas. Yet, the TTP gained legitimacy from local populace in the tribal belt who had been long denied social justice and economic development (Cassidy, 2012, p. 72). Moreover, Pakistani Taliban movement seemed “more functional and transparent” in handling with economic issues, social justice and offered “some degree of empowerment” to the poor people in tribal region (Aziz, 2008).

In addition, Taliban dealt strictly with Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) and modern educational institutions especially female institutions that could cause ideological or political challenges for the movement. In a period of one year (2006 till 2007), the Taliban killed 61 teachers and closed 12 local and 25 foreign NGOs in tribal areas. Pakistani Taliban also increased kidnapping of security and state officials to bolster the movement. For example, Taliban kidnapped more than 200 Pakistan army soldiers in South Waziristan on August 30, 2007 to put pressure on government to release Taliban prisoners. Taliban set free 213 soldiers on November 4, 2007 after the government freed 25 militants under a prisoners’ exchange made possible by a 21-member Peace Jirga (Rana, 2008).

As far as Taliban operations were concerned, several areas of erstwhile FATA had been used by Taliban in order to regroup, rearm and attack US-led coalition forces in Afghanistan and Pakistani security forces in tribal areas. Taliban also increased their presence in settled districts of KP province (Norell, 2007). Surprisingly, the MMA was often at odds with Pakistani Taliban groups. The MMA politicians acknowledged the growth of Taliban’s power and influence but at the same time, they certainly “played an indirect role in facilitating the spread of the insurgency” by making no serious effort to check Taliban advances in KP. The MMA government “indecisive response” to *Tehreek-e-Nafaz-e-Shariat-e-Mohammadi* (TNSM-was active in Malakand, Swat and Dir) and TTP expanding influence in Swat helped Taliban to gain control of these areas (White, 2008, p. 56). Besides, administration in Swat and the six Frontier Regions (small administrative units in erstwhile FATA adjoining settled areas of KP province) did nothing to “alert national authorities” about the ‘creeping Talibanization’ and growing militancy (Abbas, 2010).

Meanwhile, a range of commanders in Pakistani Taliban movement conducted operations in several different agencies separately. In December 2007, several of those commanders “loosely unified” under the banner of Tehreek-e-Taliban Pakistan (TTP). According to an analyst, Al-Qaeda also played a pivotal role in the creation of TTP. Documents recovered from the hideout of an Al-Qaeda commander, Hamza Rabia, in Gujrat in 2004 revealed that Al-Qaeda leadership in Pakistan was not in favour of fighting with Pakistan army and sought “to keep their focus on the ‘snake head’” (United States). The raison d’être of the creation of the TTP can be witnessed in this strategy of Al-Qaeda to stay focused on US-led coalition forces in Afghanistan and left the TTP to directly engage with Pakistan army (Ilahi, 2010, p. 133). In sum, it was between late 2001 and 2007 that the blend of increasingly militant radical groups, Al-Qaeda and Afghan Taliban ‘coexisted’ in the tribal belt, Frontier Regions and Swat valley under “favourable conditions” for “cooperation and regeneration.” This coupled with ineffective military strategies of United States and Pakistan in tribal areas and beyond led to the emergence of Tehreek-e-Taliban Pakistan, which over the years had transformed into an “existential threat” to the country (p. 72). To counter this threat, *Pakistanas a frontline state in the US-led ‘War on Terror’ launched military operations in Swat (2009) and South Waziristan (2009) which disrupted the TTP command and control system. Later, Pakistan Army’s Operation Zarb-e-Azb in North Waziristan (2014) destroyed TTP’s network which improved security situation.*

3. The Emergence of the Al-Qaeda-Punjabi Taliban-TTP Nexus

The most damaging impact of Pakistan’s engagement in the US-led ‘War on Terror’ was the growing radicalization, and ‘linking and overlapping’ of Punjab based Kashmir-focused groups and sectarian militant outfits with Al-Qaeda and the militants in tribal areas. This Nexus posed the gravest threat to Pakistan’s security and social harmony. In fact, to take ‘revenge’ of the US-led military campaign in Afghanistan, ‘a five-member coalition’ of the militant groups was established in 2001 under the ‘spiritual leadership’ of Mufti Nizamuddin Shamzai, Head of the Banuri madaris in Karachi. The coalition was named ‘Brigade 313’ and comprised Punjab based militant groups —also known as Punjabi Taliban—non-Pashtun militants belonging to different groups headquartered in Punjab (Rehman, 2011). These included: Kashmir-focused groups; LT, JM,

Harkat-ul-Jihad al-Islami (HuJI), Harkat-ul- Mujahideen al-Alami (HuMA); and the sectarian outfits, Sipah Sahaba Pakistan and Lashkar-e-Jhangvi (LJ). ‘Brigade 313’ soon conducted attacks on Christians in Murree, Islamabad and Taxila in reprisal for American invasion and occupation of Afghanistan. It was also alleged to be responsible for abduction and killing of American journalist, Daniel Pearl in Karachi. Furthermore, it carried out attack on General Musharraf in Rawalpindi in December 2003 (“Sectarianism Strikes,” 2004). This incident “clearly indicated a nexus between the ‘Punjabi Taliban’ and Al-Qaeda while showing their penetration in some segments of the armed forces as more than fifty Air Force personnel linked to JM were charged”, for the attack on General Musharraf (Haque, 2011).

During the same time, in tribal areas, a variety of small independent Pashtun, Taliban militant groups and Punjabi Taliban started to network one another while Pakistani security forces kept their focus on hunting down Al-Qaeda and affiliated foreign militants. According to Clarke (2011), throughout this process “Pakistani Taliban never merged into organizational structure of the Mullah [Muhammad] Omar-led Afghan Taliban” (‘though they repeatedly pledged their allegiance to Mullah Muhammad Omar’). Clarke concluded that due to “its more decentralized nature and independence from Mullah Omar, the TTP gravitated more towards Al-Qaeda than its Afghan counterpart.” Certainly, TTP had increasingly financed by Al-Qaeda, portrayed by Pakistani Interior Minister, Rehman Malik, as “the front face of Al-Qaeda.” It is important to note that TTP growing associations with Al-Qaeda was witnessed in Taliban’s rhetoric as well tactics (Valentine, 2010, p. 234). Al-Qaeda provided ideological, strategic, tactical and logistical assistance to TTP which, in turn, became expert in the use of Improvised Explosive Device (IED) and suicide bombings against Pakistan security forces and civilians (Clarke, 2011).

It is worth noting that Pakistan military’s Operation Silence in July 2007 cemented ties between Al-Qaeda, TTP and Punjab based militants. The ill-planned and poorly conducted Operation Silence to evict ‘suspected militants’ from Islamabad’s Lal Masjid (Red Mosque) and its affiliated female madrassah, Jamia Hafsa led to creation of various ‘splinter groups’ from Punjab based militants (Roul, 2010). These splinter groups joined hands with Al-Qaeda and Taliban (Mir, 2011). According to one estimate, “more than 5,000 individuals” from madaris in southern and northern parts of Punjab province joined militant training camps in North and South Waziristan in the wake of this Operation (Khan, 2010a). The operation also resulted in the emergence of some fiercest ‘splinter groups’ and some new militant groups called ‘Lal Masjid affectees’ (Abbas, 2010). Two prominent new groups were Junood-ul- Hafsa (soldiers of Hafsa), and ‘the Ghazi Abdul Rashid Shaheed Brigade’ or Ghazi Force, which was named for slain deputy leader of the Red Mosque Abdul Rashid Ghazi. Junoodul Hafsa operated out of Ghaljo area of the Orakzai tribal area and the adjacent Hangu district and targeted security forces and military installations in parts of KP, Punjab and Islamabad (Z. Khan, 2010). Ghazi Force established links with TTP, ‘Brigade 313’ and Al-Qaeda, and worked closely with the TTP during the Operation Rah-e-Rast in Swat in 2009 (Roul, 2010). Commenting on the ideological links between Al-Qaeda and Punjab based militant groups, Byman (2005) made the following observation:

“These organizations share an ideological affinity with Al-Qaeda, believing in the need for an Islamic government, the importance of jihad as an individual duty, the corruption of the most Muslim regimes, and the fundamental hostility of India and the United States.”

Most importantly, the cooperation among Punjab based militant groups and TTP had developed to the point that leaders of Punjabi Taliban were “represented in the TTP’s 40-member shura [Council]” (Khan, 2010b). Reportedly, Punjabi Taliban ‘shuttled’ between tribal areas and the rest of country to provide “logistical support” to Al-Qaeda and TTP to carry out operations in Pakistan. Tariq Pervez, a renowned counterterrorism expert, described the nexus between these groups succinctly by pointing out that “ideas, logistics, cash” was obtained from the Gulf region. Al-Qaeda provided “the chemistry”, Punjabi Taliban planned the attacks, while TTP offered “the martyrs” (Chakrabarti, 2009).

Al-Qaeda-Punjabi Taliban-TTP Nexus’ Strategy and Implications for Pakistan’s Security

Al-Qaeda-Punjabi Taliban-TTP Nexus’ Strategy to attack Pakistani security forces, innocent citizens and Western interest spread an environment of fear and anxiety in population.

i. Engagement of Al-Qaeda-Punjabi Taliban-TTP Nexus on Multiple Fronts

Al-Qaeda, Punjab-based militants and TTP Nexus recognized that they could put Pakistani security forces “at maximum disadvantage” by “engaging them on multiple fronts” to force the army to end operations in tribal area (Paris, 2010). Therefore, militants extended their operations in various parts of the country, including Punjab province, Islamabad, Karachi, Quetta and AJK apart from tribal region and KP province. The terrorists attacked security forces as well as soft targets that they considered were involved in ‘anti-Islamic activities’ such as banks, CD and barber shops, internet cafés or targets that were ‘easy to hit’ owing to “less stringent

security” such as educational institutions, mosques, restaurants, press clubs, markets and even hospitals. The suicide bombings targeting the campus of International Islamic University in Islamabad and Meena Bazaar Peshawar in October 2009, the National Bank of Pakistan in Rawalpindi in November 2009, the Moon Market in Lahore in December 2009 and civil hospital in Quetta in April 2010 are a few cases in point (Pakistan Security Report 2009, 2010; Pakistan Security Report 2010, 2011). These attacks not only caused higher civilian casualties but also reflected the ‘growing radicalization’ in the society.

Al-Qaeda-Punjabi Taliban-TTP Nexus cooperated and coordinated to strike targets deep inside Punjab province in the wake of 2007 Operation Silence. Terrorist and suicide attacks inside the country increased exponentially since Pakistan military’s operation in Swat and South Waziristan in 2009 as shown in Figure 1. In Punjab only, there had been a total of 33 suicide attacks from August 2007 to March 2010. During these three years, over 600 people were killed in suicide attacks and 112 lost their lives in bomb explosions and other incidents of terrorism (Abbas, 2010). A prominent security analyst Ikram Sehgal noted that “with the collapse of the Taliban in South Waziristan and Swat, and with them being pushed on the back foot in North Waziristan and Orakzai,” the TTP and Al-Qaeda, “will try to reactivate these cells [in South Punjab] and make them effective” (“Punjabi Taliban,” 2010). This development shifted the “centre of gravity of the war zone” from tribal areas, more to Punjab in 2009. Pakistani authorities believed that the attack on Sri Lankan cricket team in Lahore in March 2009, the unprecedented attack on the military’s General Headquarters in the Garrison City, Rawalpindi in October 2009 and the suicide attack on Special Investigation Agency in Lahore on March 2010 were examples of ‘combined operations’ of this Nexus. Similarly, Badar Mansoor and Punjabi Mujahidin in collaboration with TTP carried out December 2010 bombing at the University of Karachi that wounded four students (Khan, 2010b; Waraich, 2009). In June 2014, The Islamic Movement of Uzbekistan (IMU) and TTP carried out a high-impact attack on Karachi’s international airport. A member of TTP said, “We admit we carried out this attack with the help of our other brotherly mujahideen groups” (Hassan, 2014).

Note: Data Collected by Author from Pakistan Security Report of 2007, 2008, 2009, 2010, 2011, 2012, 2013 & 2014. Pakistan Institute for Peace Studies.

Moreover, militants extended their operations to AJK. On AJK front, two suicide attacks occurred during 2009 and three suicide attacks and two bomb blasts took place in 2010. Al-Qaeda affiliated ‘Lashkar-e-Zil (Shadow Army, LZ)’ was suspected to be involved in these attacks. According to Syed Saleem Shahzad, LZ comprised TTP, ‘Brigade 313’ and foreign militant groups such as Afghan insurgents as well as former Iraqi Republican Guards (Pakistan Security Report 2009, 2010).

ii. Increasing Sectarian and Sub-Sectarian Violence

Al-Qaeda, TTP and Punjabi Taliban Nexus had been “exploiting sectarian divisions” and cleavages in the country, particularly, Lahore, Karachi and Quetta to “undermine the state’s legitimacy and authority” (Humayun & Jiwani, 2011). Between 2001 and June 2013, a total of 3,518 citizens were killed while 6,261 injured in sectarian violence, triple the casualty figure of 1989-2000 (Sectarian Violence in Pakistan, n.d.). The number of sectarian attacks and clashes increased by 90 percent from 80 in 2007 to 152 in 2010; and by 53

percent from 139 in 2011 to 213 in 2012. Analysts argued that majority of the sectarian attacks were carried out by Lashkar-e-Jhangvi (LJ) which was deeply “inspired by Al-Qaeda’s ideology” (Z. Khan, 2010). But Shi’ite sectarian group, Sipah-e-Muhammad Pakistan, was also involved in most incidents of sectarian violence in different parts of the country (Pakistan Security Report 2012, 2013). It is important to note that Al-Qaeda, the TTP and the LJ held Iran and the Shi’ites responsible for facilitating the US occupation of Iraq and accused them of collaborating with the US against Saddam Hussein. Therefore, the LJ attacked not only Shi’ite targets, but also symbolic Iranian targets. For instance, the TTP and the LJ both claimed responsibility for the suicide attacks on ‘Al-Quds Day procession’ in Quetta on September 3, 2010. The attack caused 55 people dead and over 200 wounded (Raman, 2010). Beyond Pakistan’s urban centers, TTP and sectarian outfits “exploited sectarian” rifts in the tribal areas such as Kurram to mount the pressure on Pakistani security forces. The ‘Talibanization’ of Orakzai (the tribal area has 10 percent Shi’ite population) played a key role in fueling the sectarian conflict, as SSP and LJ amalgamated their agendas with the TTP to target the Shiite population there (Khan, 2010c).

Furthermore, the intra-sectarian fault-line (Deobandi-Barelvi) also broke out giving a new dimension to the sectarian conflict. Consequently, the Sunni-Barelvi (whom the Ahl- Hadith/Wahabis and Deobandi Taliban consider ‘as kafir or non-believers’ because Barelvi believe in veneration of Muslim saints, and intercession with Allah by Muslim saints) were targeted frequently. In April 2006, in an act of grave provocation, the entire apex leadership of the Barelvi sect was slaughtered by a suicide bomber in Karachi. In March 2009, Taliban blew up the shrine of a 17th Century Sufi poet of the Pashto language, Rehman Baba in Peshawar (“Sufi Shrine,” 2009). On July 1, 2010, more than 45 persons were killed by the two suicide bombers at the shrine of 11th-century saint, Abul Hassan Ali Hajvery, commonly known as Data Ganj Bakhsh, in Lahore (Data Darbar Attack, 2010). These attacks were widely condemned and increased the rifts between Deobandi and Barelvi sects. It could be argued that the sectarian violence in Pakistan has the potential to be a major disruptive issue to foment instability and shatter people confidence on state’s authority (Humayun & Jiwani, 2011).

iii. Militant attacks on Western interests in Pakistan

The post 9/11 period saw an increasing tendency by Al-Qaeda-Punjabi Taliban- TTPNexus to target the Western interests in Pakistan which included: attacks on US and Western consulate and embassies, Western businesses, NATO oil tankers and containers, and the beheadings of kidnapped foreigners. In 2002, Harkatul Mujahideen Al-Alami—emerged from HuM—executed a string of attacks in Karachi against Western interests, including the attack on US Consulate in June 2002. On March 2, 2006, a suicide bomber blew up his car near the US Consulate in Karachi, killing four people including an American diplomat, David Fyfe (“Karachi Hit,” 2006). The attack took place a day before the US President George Bush reached Pakistan on his official visit. Moreover, between 2008 and 2012, 361 attacks were recorded on terminals of companies, oil tankers and containers transporting supplies to NATO forces in Afghanistan (Pakistan Security Report 2012, 2013). In 2013, 50 attacks were carried out on NATO supply vehicles (Pakistan Security Report 2013, 2014). Abdullah Azzam Brigade, a militant group affiliated with TTP, sought to undermine the US- led mission in Afghanistan by carrying out frequent attacks on NATO oil tankers and containers (Masood, 2011).

Note: Pakistan Security Report 2010. (2011). Pakistan Institute for Peace Studies.

Militant attacks on Western interests in Pakistan damaged its political relations with Western countries. For instance, Pakistan and Poland saw a heated tension when Pakistani Taliban abducted a Polish engineer, Piotr Stanczak, in September 2008 near Attock in Punjab province. He was beheaded by militants in February 2009, after talks with Pakistani government for the release of captured Taliban failed (Pakistan Security Report 2010, 2011). Poland alleged that the militants had the ‘support’ of some Pakistani officials and demanded the arrest of the militants. While Islamabad rejected the accusation, Polish government requested help from US in their efforts to apprehend the killers (“Poland Asks US,” 2009). Similarly, Pakistan relations with Denmark faced set back when a suicide bomber with links to Al-Qaeda, blew up an explosive-laden car outside the Danish Embassy in June 2008, killing at least eight persons and injuring 30 others. Al-Qaeda confirmed that attack was an answer to the presence of Danish troops in Afghanistan (“Al-Qaeda Claims,” 2008). By spreading terror, Al-Qaeda-Punjabi Taliban-TTP Nexus paralysed the social structure of Pakistan. Due to the general climate of fear, people used to avoid organised gatherings and visiting public places like shrines, markets, churches, and mosques. This continuous state of fear made the society psychologically insecure. People were unable to understand how religion was being misrepresented by the extremists to instigate “anti-West and anti-state emotions” and killing innocent people (Abbasi, 2013).

iv. Attacks on Western Foreign Aid Groups in Pakistan

Al-Qaeda-TTP-Punjab based Taliban Nexus also attacked people working for foreign aid groups and NGOs in Pakistan. They issued statements, saying such organizations were working against the principles of Islam by trying to “convert Muslims and employing women.” In 2008, militants killed four Pakistanis working for Plan International, a British-based children development organization that focused on helping children in District Mansehra in KP (“Pakistan Attack Kills,” 2010). In November 2008, an American worker of United States Agency for International Development (USAID), Stephen D. Vance, was shot and killed on his way to work in Peshawar (Perlez & Khan, 2009). On March 10, 2010, over a dozen militants stormed the office of World Vision International, a US-based Christian charity, assisting survivors of the 2005 Kashmir earthquake in Mansehra. The attack killed six people including two women (“Pakistan Attack Kills,” 2010). Such attacks greatly hampered aid and development efforts in the poor and backward areas of the country. Moreover, Pakistani emergency workers also reported high levels of depression and trauma exposure, including terror attacks with relatively high prevalence estimates for mental health disorders (Razik et al., 2013).

v. Al-Qaeda and Affiliates Serious Plots against the West with roots in tribal areas

The Nexus also plotted attacks against the Western targets outside Pakistan because these militant groups had become “ideologically committed” to Al-Qaeda and “global jihad.” In addition, such attacks boosted “their

prestige,” and sent a message to the government and public of the target country to “review its policies” of engagement in the ‘War on Terror’ (Cruikshank, 2010).

It is interesting to note that the TTP provided training facilities to Al-Qaeda’s recruiters to carry out attacks in the West. For example, TTP trained a team of eight would-be suicide bombers to attack the subway system in Barcelona. The plan was thwarted in January 2008. A Pakistani Taliban spokesman Maulvi Omar claimed in a videotaped interview that “those suicide bombers were under pledge to Baitullah Mehsud” and were sent because of the Spain military’s engagement in Afghanistan (Bergen & Hoffman, 2010). The TTP also trained and assisted an American recruit of Pakistani origin, Faisal Shahzad, in his failed attempt to detonate a car bomb in Times Square on May 1, 2010 (Weiser & Moynihan, 2010). Similarly, in 2006, Islamic Jihad Union (IJU), a splinter group of Islamic Movement of Uzbekistan (IMU), trained the German ‘Sauerland group’—two Germans and a Turkish resident in Germany—in the tribal areas to detonate the US Ramstein airbase in Germany in 2007; however, that plot was thwarted (“Four Jailed,” 2010).

Reportedly, Al-Qaeda was involved in July 2005 bombings in London, which killed 52 people (“Tributes Paid,” 2009). According to security officials in United Kingdom (UK), Pakistan remained “most vulnerable” due to the “presence of Al-Qaeda’s sanctuaries” there. They alleged that all seven of those convicted, for the ‘UK fertilizer bomb plot’ to target civilians in London in March 2004, trained in tribal areas by Al-Qaeda in 2003 (Cruikshank, 2010). In a Statement to the House of Commons on October 14, 2009, the then British Prime Minister, Gordon Brown, claimed that “three-quarters of the most serious terror plots against the UK have roots in the border and mountain areas of Afghanistan and Pakistan,” and the major threat to UK “still emanates from Al-Qaeda and Pakistan.” Gilles de Kerchove, the counterterrorism coordinator of the European Union (EU), argued that after 9/11, “radicalized European nationals and residents are traveling to conflict areas or attending terrorist training camps and returning to Europe” (Finn & Miller, 2010). Al-Qaeda, TTP and other affiliates’ terror plots against the West contributed to increasing attention of the international community towards the potential impact of Pakistan’s fragility and instability on regional and global peace and stability. In July 2010, the British premier David Cameron, during his visit to India accused Pakistan of promoting the “export of terror, whether to India or whether to Afghanistan or anywhere else in the world” (“Pakistan Must Not,” 2010). Such statements reflected “an emerging international discourse that looked at Pakistan as a country hopelessly degenerating into anarchy and therefore, justifying, eventually, external military interventions” (Mezzera, & Aftab, 2009). But this discourse totally neglected Islamabad’s commitment in the War which was demonstrated by Pakistan’s troop ‘surge’ from 60,000 in 2001-2003 to 140,000 in 2009 and 150,000 in 2014 along Pak-Afghan border; significantly more than the 100,000 troops committed by 43 countries in Afghanistan. Moreover, Pakistan lost over 60,000 lives since 2002 and needed peace on its border regions to improve its security situation.

4. The Increased Linkages between Narco-Trade, Organized Crime and Terrorism

In post 9/11 era, various militant groups joined hands with drug traffickers, criminals, smugglers and timber mafia to finance their activities in Pakistan. Some senior intelligence and law enforcement officials revealed interesting data about funding sources of TTP as shown in Table.

Table	
Sources of TTP Funding	
Donations & Extortions	50 percent
Crimes (Kidnappings & Bank Robberies etc)	20 percent
Drug/Narco-Trade	30 percent

Note: Siddiqi, A. B. (2010). Taliban’s Income All Termed Illegal. *Central Asia online*.

http://centralasiaonline.com/cocoon/caii/xhtml/en_GB/features/caii/features/pakistan/2010/04/16/feature-02

By one United Nations estimate, approximately, US\$1 billion of drugs trafficked (via Nangarhar-Kunar in Eastern Afghanistan) into tribal region annually, that was under the influence of TTP and Al-Qaeda affiliates. Taliban collected toll tax from the drug traffickers to purchase weapons, and recruit other fighters, and in turn, provided traffickers security (United Nations, 2010, p. 249). According to Pakistan military estimates, Pakistani Taliban collected 200 million dollars annually from drug money (Mufti, 2009). Traffickers were also taxed for medical expenses of injured Taliban fighters. Furthermore, Taliban also collected tax on NATO containers. It was reported that militants received between 2,000-5,000 rupees per truck and per NATO container or oil tanker (Vira & Cordesman, 2011).

Pakistani Taliban operated through a “network of sleeper cells, financiers” and supporters across the country that assisted TTP to earn money for its activities. In 2008, it was reported that TTP kidnapped seventy persons from Karachi and Lahore “as revenue boosting exercise” (Valentine, 2010, p. 240). It was reported in

2013 that at least 42 militant and criminal groups were involved in extortion and kidnapping in KP and 30 in Karachi (Pakistan Security Report 2013, 2014). According to the Federal Interior Ministry, “of the dozen bank robberies that occurred in Karachi in 2009, 80 percent could be traced back to the individuals based in the tribal areas, who were believed to be working for the TTP” (Siddiqi, 2010). It was estimated that between November 2008 and April 2009 alone, TTP’s network in Karachi generated at least Rs. 250 million through kidnapping and extorting fuel contractors, who delivered fuel for US-led coalition forces in Afghanistan (Clarke, 2011, p. 98). These profits helped the “TTP carry out its operations and fund organizational management” (Siddiqi, 2010). By one intelligence estimate, over 1000 million rupees were raised by criminals in Karachi between January 2007 and January 2009 to finance TTP (Yusuf, 2009).

Another source of TTP income was smuggling of consumer goods, luxury vehicles, timber, precious minerals and weapons. A Pakistani senior intelligence official reported that almost 15 to 20 percent of the Taliban finances were being borne out through tobacco smuggling. In Khyber tribal district, Mangal Bagh, the leader of pro-Taliban Lashkar-e-Islam, and a rival militant group Lashkar-Ansar (LA) in the same area, collected tax from a notorious drug baron, who was involved in smuggling of illegally produced international cigarette brands such as Marlboro, 555, Benson & Hedges, Dunhill to Afghanistan, though his factory in Bara town of Khyber tribal area. Similarly, the illegally produced cigarettes in Kohat and Bannu districts of KP were smuggled to Afghanistan via Miranshah in North Waziristan. This area was under the control of pro-Al Qaeda, IMU that received substantial sums of money for providing security to the convoys (Shah, 2010). The ‘timber mafia’ was also responsible for funding militancy in KP and erstwhile FATA. According to Federal Investigation Agency (FIA) reports, local Taliban and militant groups affiliated to Jaish-e-Muhammad, operating in district Mansehra and Batagram, obtained financial support from the local timber mafia. The timber and gemstone smugglers in Swat provided active support to the Taliban when the area was under the grip of Maulvi Fazlullah between 2007 and March 2009 (Shamsie, 2010).

CONCLUSION

Pakistan’s engagement in the US-led ‘War on Terror’ resulted in increasing radicalization of segments of Pakistani society, growing crime-terror nexus, rising tide of terrorism, sectarian and sub-sectarian violence. In effect, Pakistan’s endorsement of the US-led coalition ‘War on Terror’ spurred new cooperation between Al-Qaeda, TTP and Punjabi Taliban. This Nexus threatened Pakistan’s domestic stability and weakened the social and political fabric of the society. The Nexus also started to use Pakistani territory to launch attacks on US-led coalition forces in Afghanistan and target Western countries and their interests abroad. This adversely impacted on Pakistan’s genuine political and strategic interests in the region and beyond despite Pakistan’s tremendous contributions in the ‘War on Terror’.

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